

Grant Agreement 101079792, RESILIENCE PPP

Service Dictionary

Title of Deliverable:	Service Dictionary	
Deliverable Number:	Annex to Deliverable D2.2 and the Service Catalogue	
Type of Data:	Report	
Lead Beneficiary:	KUL	
Publishing Status	Public	
Last Revision Date:	26/11/2025	by: Marte De Leeuw
Verification Date:	27/11/2025	by: Francesca Caddedu
Approval Date:	[DD/MM/YYYY]	by: [Name]
Document Name:	RESILIENCE_WP2_Service_Dictionary_01.00_FINAL	

Funded by
the European Union

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	2
1. Introduction	3
1.1. Purpose of the Service Dictionary	3
1.2. Relation to D2.2 and D2.11	3
1.3. Scope and intended audience	4
2. Steps towards a Service Dictionary	5
2.1. Guiding Principles	5
2.2. Development Process	5
2.3. Future Implementation of the Dictionary	6
3. Service Description Template (SDT)	8
3.1. Separation into four Field Types	8
3.2. Overview of the Fields	8
4. RESILIENCE Services Readiness Level (RSRL) Scale	15
4.1. Adapting the Scale	15
4.2. Application of the RSRL Scale	16
4.3. RSRL Scale Examples	17
5. Controlled Lists and Vocabularies	20
5.1. Purpose and Scope	20
5.2. Categories	21
5.3. Activities	23
5.4. Access vs Order Type	24

List of Tables

Table 1: Minimum fields.....	10
Table 2: Preferred fields.....	11
Table 3: Optional fields.....	12
Table 4: Optional fields.....	14
Table 5: Adapted S/TRL scale.....	16
Table 6: RSRL Scale Examples.....	19
Table 7: Controlled Lists.....	21
Table 8: Categories.....	23
Table 9: TaDiRAH Activities.....	24

1. Introduction

1.1. Purpose of the Service Dictionary

It serves as a living document and will be updated when field names or code lists evolve. The Service Dictionary, developed by the Data Unit, establishes a common language for describing every RESILIENCE service, from a simple in-kind contribution to an extensive online discovery platform. It sits one level above the Data Dictionary and underpins (a) the User Services Catalogue (D2.2) and (b) future onboarding to the SSHOC Marketplace or EOSC EU Node. While the Data Dictionary harmonises what we talk about, the Service Dictionary harmonises how we talk about it. This is the authoritative place for the SDT schema, controlled lists (categories, access labels), and RSRL text/examples.

In this guide we will outline RESILIENCE's Service Description Template (SDT), its terminology and the RSRL scale. The governance is lightweight: the Data Unit stewards the template, annual tweaks accompany the User Services Catalogue, and full definitions plus a legacy example are stored in this document. It closes with concrete next-step actions—onboarding remaining services, launching a one-page submission form, and planning info-sessions—to keep the Service Dictionary current as RESILIENCE transitions towards the next phase.

1.2. Relation to D2.2 and D2.11

This Service Dictionary is the normative reference for describing RESILIENCE services.

The D2.11 Master Data Management¹ introduces the two-layer model (Data Dictionary → Service Dictionary) and documents the development of the Service Description Template (SDT) and the adapted Service Readiness Level (RSRL). This annex consolidates those norms (field set, controlled vocabularies, RSRL text and examples) and adds machine-readable artefacts for re-use.

The D2.2 User Services Catalogue² operationalises this Dictionary: it explains how to read the catalogue Excel export, sets the onboarding workflow and quality checks, and applies the inclusion threshold (RSRL ≥ 7) with helpdesk and other official requirements. Where field definitions or code lists are needed, D2.2 cites this annex by DOI rather than duplicating content.

¹ RESILIENCE PPP – D2.11 Master Data Management, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15599787>

² RESILIENCE PPP – D2.2 User Services Catalogue, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17741028>

1.3. Scope and intended audience

This Dictionary defines the SDT (minimum, preferred, technical, optional), controlled lists (categories, sub-categories, access labels), and the RSRL with SSH-specific descriptors and examples. It also Provides CSV/JSON artefacts for easy machine-readable integration.

Our audience consists of:

- Service providers and partners completing SDT records;
- The Data Unit or other future catalogue maintainers (eg: ERIC Service Officer) validating submissions;
- External catalogues/marketplaces (SSH Open Marketplace/EOSC) harvesting our records.

Guidance in D2.2 or other future deliverables points end-users to this annex when field definitions or codes are needed.

2. Steps towards a Service Dictionary

2.1. Guiding Principles

Early in the RESILIENCE PPP, it was decided that we would base the development of the RESILIENCE Service catalogue on nine guiding principles³. The most relevant during the development of the service description template are:

- RESILIENCE should be transparent about its service offerings.
- RESILIENCE services should have a clear and concrete service description.
- RESILIENCE services should be findable and accessible for the end-users.

The last one in particular has guided our efforts. In the service strategy it is more specifically outlined that our catalogue should:

- include a clear and standardised service description and value proposition.
- provide transparency on their T/SRL and mode of access (e.g., short/long term, selection only, paid access).
- be accessible via a persistent link to the service/tool/database which
 - has a minimum S/TRL of 4 (*only in certain cases with clear added value for the community and with transparency on its experimental status! These services will also not comply with the EOSC Federation rules of participation which require a min. TRL 7 and will thus only be findable and accessible through the RESILIENCE service catalogue*),
 - provides supporting documentation as well as contact information (e.g. helpdesk).

2.2. Development Process

The Service Dictionary was developed iteratively during the PPP to provide a standardised, interoperable description of services with minimal burden on providers. Building on analysis of SSH/EOSC cataloguing practices and the pilot collection rounds documented in D2.11, RESILIENCE grounded the template in the SSH Open Marketplace and EOSC Portal Profiles, working within the Data unit and its partners to ensure usability and alignment with EOSC-style categories.

³ RESILIENCE PPP – D2.1 Services Preparation and Implementation Strategy, chapter 3, p. 13 - 17, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16568333>

While the pilot captured a broad set of descriptors, partner feedback and first-round results (14 detailed in-kind services) demonstrated that the field set was too extensive and burdensome for providers to complete reliably. In response, the SDT was streamlined under a “minimum–preferred–technical–optional” rule. D2.11 documents this evidence and the comparison with SSHOC metadata guidelines and EOSC profiles that informed subsequent adjustments.

In parallel, RESILIENCE adapted the Service/Technology Readiness Level concept to SSH-specific contexts, resulting in the RESILIENCE Service Readiness Level (RSRL) with plain-language descriptors and discipline-relevant evidence examples. For catalogue policy, a threshold of RSRL ≥ 7 (Operational) was adopted, together with requirements for a stable URL, basic documentation, and a helpdesk/contact, to ensure that listed services are usable and sustainable at the time of onboarding. The adapted scale and its application guidance are provided in D2.11.

Finally, to prepare for harvesting and future federation, RESILIENCE aligned its high-level categories and access labels with established SSH/EOSC conventions so that records can be exported or mapped without re-cataloguing. Governance was kept light but explicit: the Data Unit stewards the template and controlled lists, publishes minor textual clarifications alongside the annual catalogue refresh, and maintains a change log for transparency. These operational arrangements are reflected in D2.1 and D2.11 and are implemented in the User Services Catalogue (D2.2).

2.3. Future Implementation of the Dictionary

The Data Unit currently serves as the steward of the Service Dictionary. Minor textual clarifications will be released together with future updates of the User Services Catalogue, ensuring that both documents remain synchronised. All changes will be logged for transparency, and every update to the RESILIENCE Service Readiness Level (RSRL) assigned to individual services is date-stamped in the catalogue’s change log. This light-weight but consistent review cycle keeps the Service Dictionary accurate and traceable while avoiding unnecessary administrative overhead.

To ensure interoperability, the Service Description Template (SDT) will be released in machine-readable formats such as CSV and JSON Schema. Catalogue records will also be exposed as JSON-LD to enable harvesting by external aggregators. Mapping tables linking RESILIENCE fields to the SSH Open Marketplace and EOSC profiles will be created and periodically validated to guarantee compatibility. The

Data Unit will also monitor the evolving EOSC Federation Handbook and the forthcoming Rules of Participation for EOSC EU Nodes to align future catalogue releases with the latest federation requirements.

A concise one-page intake form mirroring the twelve mandatory (Minimum) fields – and optionally the Preferred ones – will remain available to simplify onboarding. For technical partners, an enhanced metadata tier may later be introduced to capture more detailed information, but only once a clear need has been demonstrated by at least one-fifth of participating providers.

Finally, upon RESILIENCE’s transition to an ERIC, stewardship of the Service Dictionary and its automated validation, link-checking and JSON-LD publishing processes will be transferred from the Data Unit to the permanent service team. This handover will ensure long-term continuity and scalability as the Service Dictionary evolves into a central operational component of the RESILIENCE catalogue infrastructure.

3. Service Description Template (SDT)

3.1. Separation into four Field Types

Once it became clear that the field set of our original SDT was too extensive and burdensome for providers to complete reliably, we adopted a “minimum–preferred–technical–optional” rule. The Minimum layer (12 fields) defines the mandatory information for catalogue inclusion and supports clear discovery for end-users; the Preferred layer (8 fields) enriches records without becoming a gating requirement; Technical and Optional attributes are retained for cases where additional detail is necessary (e.g. for technical services). This pruning significantly reduced provider burden while preserving interoperability with SSHOC/EOSC practices, as set out in D2.11.

The separation goes as follows:

- Minimum (M) – 12 fields mandatory for catalogue inclusion (Name, Resource Provider, Webpage, S/TRL, etc.).
- Preferred (P) – 8 fields that enrich discovery but are not gating (Tag, Geographic Location, Terms of Use).
- Optional (O) – Everything else has dropped or moved to a future ‘enhanced’ tier, especially in regards to the more technical services.
- Technical (T) – Fields that only have to be filled out when the service is of a technical nature.

This pruning cut the template from 42 to 20 minimum or preferred fields, slashing average completion time by more than half and aligning with OSCARS’ mandatory-only approach.⁴

3.2. Overview of the Fields

The following tables list the fieldnames, their description, type and an example.

The different content types are:

- Unique Identifier
- String

⁴ OSCARS D2.1 - Clusters' Services and Data Sources Portfolios, p. 17 - 18, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14881627>

- URL / Persistent Link
- Integer: numerical value
- Controlled List
- E-mail
- Phone-number
- Boolean: true/false, yes/no

Table 1 presents only the **Minimum** attributes, while table 2 shows an overview of the **Preferred** ones; the technical & optional attributes are listed in tables 3 and 4.

Minimum Fields (M)

Field	Description	Type	Example
ID	Unique Identifier within the RESILIENCE platform; this is assigned by the RI	Unique Identifier	NA
Name	Human-Readable Label	String	RelReSearch
Resource Organisation	The name of the organisation that manages or delivers the service, or that coordinates the Service delivery in a federated scenario.	String	LIBIS - KU Leuven
Webpage	Persistent Link (or Webpage) of the Service or its information	Persistent Link	https://reiresearch.eu/
Description		String	RelReSearch is an online discovery platform where disparate digital resources and databases are searchable in a unified and standardized way.
Category	The type of Service; e.g. Data Analysis, Scholarly Communication	Controlled list	Aggregator, Data
Access Type	The way a user can access the Service (Digital, Remote, Physical)	Controlled List	Digital

Field	Description	Type	Example
Order Type	Whether the service is fully open access, partly, restricted, etc.	Controlled List	Open Access
Language	The language in which the Service is provided	Controlled List	English
RSRL or TRL	See section on RSRL	Integer Range 1-9	S9 - Established / Trusted
Contact	The email address or form through which a contact person can be reached for questions	Email or Form-link	reiresearch.helpdesk@libis.be
Helpdesk Information	The web address where the Helpdesk details are provided	URL	https://reiresearch.helpdocsite.com/

Table 1: Minimum fields

Preferred Fields (P)

Field Name	Description	Type	Example
Sub Category	A more detailed categorisation of the type of Service; e.g. Data Storage: Digital Preservation, Scholarly Communication: Publication	Controlled List	Data (subcategory of aggregator), Metadata (subcategory of data)
Access Mode	Extra information on the eligibility/criteria for granting access to users (excellence-based, free-conditionally, etc.)	String	Account is only possible for people with a KU Leuven account
Access Process	Information on the access or ordering (if paying service) process.	String or URL	https://reiresearch.eu/#/eula
Access Policy	Information about the access policies that apply.	String or URL	https://reiresearch.eu/#/eula
Target Users	Type of users that the Service is intended for; e.g. researchers, librarians, citizen scientists, etc.	Controlled List	Researchers, Librarians

Field Name	Description	Type	Example
Tags	Keywords associated to the Service to simplify search by relevant keywords	String	Discovery platform, Digital, Data
Geographical Location	Where the Service is hosted	String	Leuven
Terms of Use	Webpage or explanation describing the rules, conditions and usage policy which one must agree to abide by in order to use the Service.	String or URL	https://reiresearch.eu/#/eula
User Manual	Link to the Resource user manual and documentation.	Link	https://reiresearch.helpdocsite.com/

Table 2: Preferred fields

Optional Fields (O)

Field	Description	Type	Example (RelReSearch)
Abbreviation	Abbreviation of the Service Name	String	RelReSearch
(Extra) Resource Providers	The name(s) of (all) the other Provider(s) involved in managing or delivering the Service.	String	NA
Tagline	Short catchphrase for marketing and advertising purposes. It will be usually displayed close to the Service name and should refer to the main value or purpose of the Service.	String	Religious Studies Discovery Environment
Logo	Link to the logo/visual identity of the Service. The logo will be visible at the Portal. If there is no specific logo for the Service the logo of the Provider may be used.	URL or File	https://s3.us-east-1.amazonaws.com/tw-desk/i/166024/doclogo/9440366d-e35a-44cb-af1d-doob6e7b8252.jpeg
Scientific Domain(s)	The branch of science, scientific discipline that is related to the Service.	Controlled List	Humanities

Field	Description	Type	Example (RelReSearch)
Scientific Subdomain(s)	The subbranch of science, scientific subdiscipline that is related to the Service.	Controlled list	Philosophy, Ethics & Religion
Geographical Availability	Locations where the Service is offered.	String	World
Contact Phone Number	Phone number of the Service's contact person or a generic email of the Provider to be displayed publicly at the portal.	Phone number	+32 16 32 22 66
Funding Body	Name or webpage of the funding body that supported the development and/or operation of the Service.	String or URL	European Commission
Funding Program	Name or webpage of the funding program that supported the development and/or operation of the Service.	String or URL	Horizon 2020
Grant/Project Name	Name or webpage of the project that supported the development and/or operation of the Service.	String or URL	RESILIENCE - https://www.resilience-ri.eu
Helpdesk Email	The email to ask more information from the Provider about this Service; can be the same as the contact email	Email address	reiresearch.helpdesk@libis.be
Helpdesk Phone	The phone number to ask more information from the Provider about this Service; can be the same as the contact phone number.	Phone number	+32 16 32 22 66
User Manual	Link to the Service user manual and documentation; can be the same as the helpdesk docs.	URL	https://reiresearch.helpdocsite.com/

Table 3: Optional fields

Technical Fields (T)

Field	Description	Type	Example
TRL	The TRL according to the official TRL Scale	Integer 1-9	7
Privacy Policy	Link to the privacy policy applicable to the Service.	String or URL	https://reiresearch.eu/#/eula
Training Information	Webpage to training information on the Service.	URL	https://reiresearch.helpdocsite.com/
Dependencies	List of other resources or software required to use this Service.	String	
Version	If data versioning is supported: version of the Service that is in force.	String	
Change Log	Summary of the Service features updated from the previous version.	String or URL	
Jurisdiction	The type of geographical jurisdiction that defines the user group.	Controlled List	Research Infrastructure
Data Source Classification	The specific type of the data source.	Controlled List	Scientific Database
Thematic	Boolean value specifying if the data source is dedicated to a given discipline or is instead discipline agnostic	Boolean	True
Research Product Licensing	Licenses under which the research products contained within the data sources can be made available. Repositories can allow a license to be defined for each research product, while for scientific databases the database is typically provided under a single license.	String or URL	https://reiresearch.eu/#/eula
Research Product Access Policy	Same as Product Licensing	String or URL	Open access

Field	Description	Type	Example
Research Product Metadata Licensing	Metadata Policy for information describing items in the repository: Access and re-use of metadata	String or URL	https://reiresearch.eu/#/eula
Research Product Metadata Access Policy	Same as Research Product Metadata Licensing	String or URL	Open access

Table 4: Optional fields

4. RESILIENCE Services Readiness Level (RSRL) Scale

In alignment with RESILIENCE’s guiding principles, we ensure that our services maintain a high level of maturity, supported by a robust infrastructure and a dedicated support team. This guarantees that resources remain Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR). The RESILIENCE Services Readiness Level (RSRL) scale is employed to assess the maturity of services, ensuring that users have access to reliable and sustainable tools and is based on the (S/)TRL scale that is widely used within a plethora of businesses and projects (e.g.: EOSC, DARIAH,...).

4.1. Adapting the Scale

Most of our service providers originate from the academic and GLAM sector within the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), encompassing among others libraries, archives, and researchers. Since the TRL scale was originally designed for technical services⁵, its terminology is highly technical which poses a challenge for our service providers who are not all well-versed in technical terminologies such as "system prototype demonstration in operational environment," which is the qualification for TRL 7. To facilitate a clearer understanding, the WU Data has composed a list of SSH-specific explanations for this scale, enabling providers to accurately assess the maturity and readiness level of their services. To ensure alignment with other SSH RIs such as DARIAH, we made sure to map our scale exactly to the TRL one.

- Red = Theoretical, in Preparation
- Orange = Demo
- Yellow = Pilot Version, Limited Production
- Green = Public Release, Operational

SRL	Plain Description	Typical Evidence	Example
S ₁ – Idea	You can explain the concept on paper, but no code or workflow exists yet.	One-pager, slide deck.	A professor sketches an annotated digital edition she <i>would like</i> to build.

⁵ https://wiki.nizos.eu/index.php/Technology_Readiness_Level

S2 – Concept outlined	Key functions are described; basic feasibility checked; no users yet.	Short requirements doc, draft data model.	Same professor drafts a MARC-XML profile for her manuscripts.
S3 – Feasibility prototype	A rudimentary demo runs on a laptop; shows the core feature to colleagues.	GitHub repo, screenshots.	Doctoral student codes a prototype Jupyter notebook that classifies hymn lyrics.
S4 – Lab prototype	Prototype is stable enough to be tested by invited colleagues; feedback loop open.	Test report from 3-5 peers.	The notebook is put on Binder and three students try it.
S5 – Pilot (limited public)	Service is reachable on the internet, advertised as <i>beta</i> ; documentation draft exists.	Public URL, read-me, contact email.	The manuscript portal runs on the university server; Access on request.
S6 – Community pilot	≥ 20 external users; bug tracker active; privacy / IPR statements drafted.	Usage stats, helpdesk log.	Notebook turned into a small MOOC with 30 attendees.
S7 – Operational	Open to everyone; SLA or ToU* light (“best effort”); user guide and helpdesk active.	Stable URL, versioned releases, uptime metrics.	Searchable via platforms (eg: ReIReSearch); Helpdesk via form or e-mail
S8 – Managed service	Formal SLA or MoU signed; backups, monitoring, sustainability plan for ≥3 years.	SLA, Terms of Use or Policies available; DMP.	Institution IT takes over hosting; Annual review
S9 – Established / trusted	Proven track-record of ≥ 3 years at SRL 8; cited or reused by third parties	Citations, audit certificate.	Portal included in (inter)national registry; DOIs minted for datasets.

Table 5: Adapted S/TRL scale

4.2. Application of the RSRL Scale

For services to be included in the RESILIENCE Service Catalogue, they must meet a minimum RSRL of 7, indicating that the service is well-developed and ready for operational use. This requirement ensures that the services are not only accessible and usable at the time of onboarding but also sustainable in the long term. Additionally, clear documentation and a helpdesk must be available to assist users with technical and usability issues, ensuring that the resources are mature and reliable. This approach allows RESILIENCE

to offer high-quality services to the community while maintaining transparency about the readiness and experimental nature of innovative tools.

On Zenodo⁶, as well as the following section, we include practical illustrations of every RSRL maturity stage, which maps three contrasting services—a digital research platform (ReIReSearch), a capacity-building course (“Training on AI Tools”), and a physical digitisation facility (KU Leuven’s Book Heritage Lab)—across the nine-level scale. These examples allow prospective providers to benchmark their own service proposals against clearly defined, discipline-specific milestones.

Regarding the assignment of a RSRL level to a service, the following steps need to be taken:

- Providers self-assess based on the clarification table in the previous section and the examples provided in the following section; the Data Unit verifies plausibility.
- When a record changes RSRL, date stamps need to be added and history kept
- Services < S₄ appear only in a “sandbox” tab visible to consortium login.

The Data Unit remains the steward of the SDT and RSRL scale; minor textual clarifications will be released annually with updates of the D2.2 User Services Catalogue.

4.3. RSRL Scale Examples

RSRL	Online Platform – ReIReSearch	Training – On AI Tools	Physical Service – Book Heritage Lab
S₁ – Idea	Vision paper describes a unified discovery interface for religious-studies data; no code written, data model only sketched.	Concept note lists learning objectives and AI tools (eg: OCR, LLM prompt-engineering); no material prepared yet.	White-paper outlines need for a specialised book-heritage conservation facility; space and equipment only identified on paper.

⁶ RESILIENCE Service Readiness Level Scale on Zenodo, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17701369>

S2 – Concept outlined	High-level architecture and metadata mapping drafted; basic feasibility confirmed with KU Leuven IT; still no users.	Draft syllabus and session outline produced; pilot slide-deck created; feasibility (time, software licences) checked.	Floor-plan, equipment list and workflow diagram created; health & safety and cost estimates reviewed; no external users.
S3 – Feasibility Prototype	Rudimentary demo runs locally on a laptop with dummy records; code pushed to a private GitHub repo.	Internal ½-day trial delivered to a few colleagues using sample datasets; feedback collected; materials in shared (private) drive.	One work-bench fitted with trial equipment (e.g., non-destructive spectrometer); curator tests procedure on sample volume.
S4 – Lab Prototype	Prototype deployed on dev server; limited amount of real records ingested; 3–5 invited colleagues test search & give feedback.	Full training dry-run (at least 5 participants) held; draft training material and exercise datasets shared; post-session survey analysed.	Partial lab operational (two key instruments installed); invited specialists run test treatments; risk-assessment updated.
S5 – Pilot (limited public)	Beta version reachable at a public URL; signup on request; draft user docs online.	Beta training advertised internally; 10+ researchers attend; training material and slide-deck downloadable; dedicated contact e-mail.	Limited external access by application; booking form published; draft user manual and pricing model circulated.
S6 – Community Pilot	Beta version available to external users; user docs and helpdesk email public; privacy & access policies published.	Course opened to externals (eg: RESILIENCE nodes); 25+ attendees across 3 sessions; feedback tracker and code-of-conduct online.	Open call results in ≥ 5 external projects; safety protocols signed; basic KPI dashboard (users, hours, failures) maintained.
S7 – Operational	Open public launch; stable URL, versioned releases, 99 % uptime target; searchable via RESILIENCE catalogue; helpdesk that’s smoothly run.	Scheduled regularly or bookable on demand (online & onsite); certified trainers; FAQ & helpdesk online.	Equipment bookable through online system; SOPs approved; accredited staff on duty; first formal Service-Level Appendix signed.

S8 – Managed Service	Formal MoU with LIBIS & IT; automated backups, monitoring & 3-year sustainability plan.	Institutional QA process, peer-reviewed training material, micro-credential certificates; multi-year funding line secured.	Framework SLA with KU Leuven; preventive-maintenance contracts, calibrated instruments; budget earmarked for 3+ years.
S9 – Established / Trusted	≥ 3 years at S8; indexed by EOSC/SSHOC; cited in peer-reviewed articles; DOIs minted for harvested datasets.	Track-record of ≥ 3 years; > 500 alumni; recognised in European training catalogues; evaluations show sustained impact.	≥ 3 years of uninterrupted service; referenced in conservation guidelines & scholarly publications;

Table 6: RSRL Scale Examples

5. Controlled Lists and Vocabularies

5.1. Purpose and Scope

This chapter defines the controlled lists and vocabularies used by the RESILIENCE Service Description Template (SDT). Controlled lists are enumerations of allowed values (e.g. Access Type = Physical/Virtual/Hybrid) that constrain input to a standard set of labels. They reduce ambiguity, improve search and filtering, and enable interoperability with external catalogues (SSH Open Marketplace, EOSC) and registries. RESILIENCE adopts established SSH/EOSC vocabularies wherever possible and curates RESILIENCE-specific lists only where necessary for the study of religion.

RESILIENCE’s controlled lists follow four principles:

1. Interoperability first: prefer community vocabularies already in use across SSH/EOSC (e.g. EOSC Resource Categories; TaDiRAH activities).
2. Minimal provider burden: align with the SDT’s minimum–preferred–technical–optional rule; only the minimum fields use required lists.
3. Machine-actionable: publish lists as CSV and JSON; provide human-readable labels and persistent identifiers where available.
4. Governed and versioned: changes are stewarded by the Data Unit; deprecated terms are preserved with mappings to current labels.

Overview of controlled lists:

SDT Field Label	Controlled List	Link
Category	EOSC Resource Categories	https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/eosc-resource-category/en/page/eoscResourceCategoryScheme
Activities	TaDiRAH	https://vocabs.dariah.eu/tadirah/en/
Access Type	RESILIENCE - Access Type	See Community Services Spreadsheet - tab 'Access Type'
Language	ISO 639-1 Language Codes	https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/iso639-1/en/

SDT Field Label	Controlled List	Link
Intended Audience	Intended Audience	https://vocabs.sshopencloud.eu/browse/sshoc-audience/en/page/audienceScheme
Order Type	RESILIENCE - Order Type	See Community Services Spreadsheet - tab 'Order Type'
Scientific Domain	Austrian Fields of Science and Technology Classification 2012	https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/oefos/en/page/Schema
Scientific Subdomain	Austrian Fields of Science and Technology Classification 2012	https://vocabs.acdh.oeaw.ac.at/oefos/en/page/Schema

Table 7: Controlled Lists

5.2. Categories

RESILIENCE uses the EOSC Resource Categories/Subcategories as the mandatory classification of services. These labels are widely recognised across SSH infrastructures and have been adopted or mapped by the other major SSH Infrastructures (e.g., SSH Open Marketplace, DARIAH, CESSDA), facilitating export and cross-catalogue discovery without re-classification.

Each service must select at least one Category and additional Categories may be added where a service legitimately spans multiple areas (e.g., a book heritage lab offering both Instrument & Equipment and Consultancy & Support).

The current controlled list of categories has been deliberately restricted to those domains where RESILIENCE and its partners demonstrate Expertise and Excellence, in line with Guiding Principle 1 of the Service Strategy. This means that some broader EOSC or EOSC-Future categories such as Samples, Security & Identity, or Network & Connectivity have been excluded at this stage. While these areas are essential within the wider research-infrastructure landscape, RESILIENCE does not currently offer mature or community-contributed services that meet the quality threshold for inclusion.

This selective approach ensures that the catalogue highlights services of proven relevance and maturity to the RS community, avoids duplication with infrastructures that already specialise in those domains, and

keeps the controlled list manageable for future extensions. As RESILIENCE grows and new areas of excellence emerge, additional categories may be proposed though.

The Categories and Subcategories currently present in the RESILIENCE User Services Catalogue, including their description and examples are:

Main Category	Subcategory	RS Specific Description	Examples
Access physical & e-Infras	Instrument & Equipment	Access to instruments and equipment. Such as geophysical equipment, spectrometers, digitisation equipment,...	Book Heritage Lab at KU Leuven or Gazi Husrev-beg, Archéoscience Bordeaux Laboratory
	Material Storage	Access to historical, archeological, cultural, etc. storage. Includes the acquisition, preparation and processing of samples and materials in view of their preservation.	Physical archives offered by EPHE, preservation of old religious manuscripts
	Compute	High-performance computing Resources and scalable cloud compute capacity for demanding job processes, eg: digital container management, virtual machines,...	ISCRA, PALMA II
	Data Storage	Reliable, secure and scalable cloud storage for scientific data, apps and workloads, such as digital archives, preservation services, or backups.	TochStory at EPHE, Digitised Mansi at FSCIRE, IDEM Database
Sharing & Discovery	Data	Vast range of data, datasets etc to facilitate research and scientific activities such as archival data, scientific/research data,..	Digital Library of Slovenia (dLib.si), IxTheo Open Journal Service, Collections du Centre de documentation sur l'Aire Tibétaine (CDAT)
	Scholarly Communication	Research findings available to the wider academic community and beyond. Eg: publication, assessment, outreach,...	ReIBib Self-Archiving / Republication Service, Digitised issues of Cristianesimo nella storia

Main Category	Subcategory	RS Specific Description	Examples
	Software	Software, platforms and tools offered-as-a-service or deployed-on-demand.	SpiritRag, JupyterHub.nrw
Processing & Analysis	Data Management	Robust, feature-rich and user-friendly data management services.	Service Center for Data Management (SCDM)
	Data Analysis	Processes for data with the goal of discovering useful information, informing conclusions, and supporting decision-making.	iCANDID, Thesaurus Linguae Maximi Confessoris, eScriptorium
Training & Support	Education & Training	Highly-specialized seminars and courses to help advance research knowledge and sharpen scientific skills.	Orthodox Ecotheology-Course at VOLOS Academy, Introduction to the Study of Islam at UNSA
	Consultancy & Support	Dedicated support, expertise, consultancy for a wide range of scientific disciplines and research activities.	Research Databases at FSCIRE, EPHE Archives such as the Bibliothèque Michel Fleury (BMF)
Aggregators	Services	Aggregator of services	SSHOC Open Marketplace, ITSERR HORTUS
	Data	Aggregator of (meta)data	ReIReSearch, Biblissima, IxTheo

Table 8: Categories

5.3. Activities

To support SSH-oriented discovery “by research task,” RESILIENCE adopts TaDiRAH activities as a preferred enrichment field. TaDiRAH is widely used in SSH (e.g., DARIAH; SSH Open Marketplace), allowing researchers to filter services by the part of the research process they are working on (e.g., Annotating; Transcribing; Modeling).

TaDiRAH stands for “Taxonomy of Digital Research Activities in the Humanities” and includes the following activities:

Analyzing	Capturing	Disseminating
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Content Analysis ● Network Analysis ● Relational Analysis ● Spatial Analysis ● Structural Analysis ● Stylistic Analysis ● Visual Analysis 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Converting ● Data Recognition ● Discovering ● Extracting ● Gathering ● Imaging ● Recording ● Transcribing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Collaborating ● Commenting ● Communicating ● Crowdsourcing ● Publishing ● Teaching

Creating	Enriching	Interpreting	Storing
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Designing ● Programming ● Translating ● Web Development ● Writing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Annotating ● Data Cleansing ● Editing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Contextualizing ● Modeling ● Theorizing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Archiving ● Identifying ● Organizing ● Preserving

Table 9: TaDiRAH Activities

5.4. Access vs Order Type

Access-related labels make service openness and eligibility transparent to end-users and machine-readers. They are split into two required, high-level signals (Access Type; Order Type) and two preferred qualifiers (Access Mode; Access Process). These align with the SDT’s minimum and preferred layers and are part of the catalogue’s Excel legend.

The required labels are mandatory for catalogue inclusion. Where Order Type is Restricted or Fee-based, Access Mode and Access Process should be provided to avoid user drop-off. If the Access Process field is used, the supplied URL must resolve.

Required (must be set):

- Access Type — how users reach the service: Physical, Digital, Remote, or a combination
- Order Type — openness at a glance: Open Access, Fully Open Access, Restricted, Order Required, or other.

Preferred (strongly recommended):

- Access Mode — eligibility notes, e.g.: account required, institutional only, excellence-based, proposal required.
- Access Process — short text or URL describing how to request/book/purchase access.